

COMPETENCY CERTIFICATION, TASK COMPLEXITY, MANAGEMENT SUPPORT, AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. The accounting information system (AIS) plays a crucial role in supporting the processes of collecting, recording, processing, and reporting reliable and timely accounting information. The effectiveness of AIS is essential for organizations, including cooperatives, in enhancing operational efficiency, producing quality information for decision-making, and ensuring accurate financial data recording. This study aims to obtain empirical evidence on the effect of competency certification, task complexity, and management support on the effectiveness of accounting information systems. The sample was selected using a non-probability purposive sampling method, involving 80 respondents. Data analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression analysis. The findings indicate that competency certification, task complexity, and management support have a positive effect on AIS effectiveness. These results also suggest that the more certifications obtained, the higher the task complexity and management support, the greater the effectiveness of AIS. The theoretical implication of this study supports the application of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) in empirical research on AIS effectiveness.

Keywords: Competency Certification; Task Complexity; Management Support; Accounting Information System Effectiveness

INTRODUCTION

A cooperative is a business entity comprised of individuals or legal entities based on cooperative principles and functions as a people's economic movement grounded in the principle of kinship. As the backbone of Indonesia's economy, cooperatives operate on the foundation of collective efforts and mutual cooperation. This aligns with the cooperative principles (Dwipradnyana et al., 2020). The technology-based information systems used by cooperatives are expected to produce high-quality information. However, in practice, cooperative operations are not always effective, even with the use of technology-based accounting information systems. Common issues include input or processing errors due to system bugs or crashes, loss of transaction data from failed storage, server downtime due to overload or unscheduled maintenance, and lack of automatic data backup systems. These problems affect transaction recording, lead to inaccurate financial decisions, hinder operations, cause member dissatisfaction, and increase the workload for employees. One of the main causes is the low effectiveness of AIS, which should otherwise enhance cooperative operations reliably and efficiently.

Most previous studies have only examined one or two variables separately without considering the simultaneous effects and interactions among factors. In practice, AIS effectiveness is influenced by a combination of individual, environmental, and technological factors. In Denpasar City, the number of cooperatives is growing, yet many remain inactive due to inadequate AIS utilization, highlighting the need for a more

focused study. Several studies have investigated factors affecting AIS effectiveness, including competency certification, task complexity, and management support. Findings by Hasanah et al. (2017), Syaifudin et al. (2022), Hamidiyah et al. (2022), and Raharjo et al. (2023) show that competency certification positively affects employee performance, while Rawis et al. (2019) found no such effect, indicating inconsistent empirical evidence that requires further clarification.

This study differs from previous research in its location, criteria for research sites, and sampling methods. Prior studies such as Ribeiro & Putra (2023) were conducted in South Denpasar, and Paramitha & Supadmi (2023) in South Kuta. This study employs both TAM and TPB theories, unlike previous studies that used only one model. Besides competency certification, task complexity is also crucial in supporting AIS effectiveness. Employees with certification are considered credible in fulfilling their duties, particularly in understanding and operating AIS accurately. Despite differing findings, many studies, such as those by Lestari & Fauzi (2023), Numberi (2022), Athambawa & Teng (2018), and Paranoan et al. (2019), suggest that competency certification significantly enhances employee performance, making it a valuable asset for optimizing cooperative human resource capacity.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM was first introduced by Fred Davis in 1986, positing that user motivation predicts system usage. According to TAM, users are likely to use a system if they perceive it as easy to use (perceived ease of use) and beneficial (perceived usefulness). It highlights the psychological and social factors affecting technology adoption. Organizations can design more user-friendly technologies that meet user expectations. In the AIS context, competency certification contributes to ease of use, task complexity relates to perceived usefulness, and management support facilitates both through training and infrastructure.

2.2 Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Developed by Martin Fishbein and Icek Ajzen in the 1980s, TPB suggests that behavioral intention is influenced not only by attitude and subjective norms but also by perceived behavioral control (Ajzen, 1991). TPB predicts human behavior based on the assumption that individuals think rationally and systematically when using available information. In the AIS context, competency certification can influence individual intentions and behavior in system usage, task complexity affects their perceived ability, and management support fosters a social environment that encourages system usage.

2.3 The Effect of Competency Certification on AIS Effectiveness

Competency certification significantly influences system effectiveness. In TAM, it contributes to ease of use, and in TPB, it shapes behavior and intention. Quality human resources are essential for effective AIS operation. Research by Lestari & Fauzi (2023), Numberi (2022), Athambawa & Teng (2018), and Paranoan et al. (2019) supports the positive impact of competency on AIS effectiveness.

H1: Competency certification positively affects accounting information system effectiveness.

2.4 The Effect of Task Complexity on AIS Effectiveness

According to TAM, perceived usefulness and ease of use influence technology adoption. TPB links task complexity to an individual's perception of their capability to operate AIS. Some employees perceive tasks as complex and challenging, while others consider them manageable. Studies by Putri & Karyada (2020), Anjani & Wirawati (2018), and Juliastini et al. (2020) indicate that task complexity negatively affects AIS effectiveness.

H2: Task complexity negatively affects accounting information system effectiveness.

2.5 The Effect of Management Support on AIS Effectiveness

Management participation supports AIS development and implementation. When management provides adequate training and resources, users gain confidence in using the system. Research by Komala (2012), Mkonya et al. (2018), Putri & Karyada (2020), Putri & Juliarsa (2023), Saraswati & Widhiyani (2024), and Ernawati et al. (2022) confirms the positive influence of management support on AIS effectiveness.

H3: Management support positively affects accounting information system effectiveness.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study adopts a quantitative approach with an associative research design to analyze the influence of competency certification, task complexity, and management support on the effectiveness of accounting information systems (AIS) in Savings and Loan Cooperatives (KSP) in Denpasar City. This approach was chosen to assess the extent of relationships among variables using empirical data. The population includes all active KSPs in Denpasar. The sample was selected using purposive sampling based on criteria such as cooperatives that have implemented digital AIS, assets above IDR 3 billion, employees with at least one year of experience in accounting, and those holding competency certification.

Data were collected using questionnaires distributed to managers and staff directly involved with AIS in each cooperative. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to present respondent characteristics and variable conditions. To assess the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable, multiple linear regression analysis was applied. Instrument testing was conducted to ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. Classical assumption tests included normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests to validate the regression model. Data processing was performed using statistical software such as SPSS.

The results are expected to explain how individual and organizational factors affect AIS effectiveness within cooperatives, particularly in Denpasar. Furthermore, t-tests, F-tests, and the coefficient of determination (R^2) were conducted to assess partial and simultaneous effects. The regression model used in this study is as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

Y = Quality of Financial Reporting

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X1 = Competency Certification

X₂ = Task Complexity
 X₃ = Management Support
 ε = Standard Error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION
Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Classification	Number of Respondents (People)	Percentage (%)
1	Age	< 50 years	69	87
		≥ 50 years	11	13
2	Gender	Man	35	44
		Woman	45	56
3	Cooperative Category	Open Loop	04	5
		Close Loop	76	95
4	Length of Service in Current Position	1-3 years	26	33
		> 3 years	54	67

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Descriptive statistics is an analytical method used to describe data based on the average (mean), standard deviation, and maximum and minimum values (Sugiyono, 2022:206). In this study, each variable was measured using a four-point Likert scale. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis of the research variables are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics Results of Research Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Competency Certification	80	8	20	16.20	3,719
Task Complexity	80	6	24	18.80	4,985
Management Support	80	6	24	19.34	5,459
Effectiveness of Accounting Information Systems	80	20	48	39.68	8,204
Valid N (listwise)	80				

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

The competency certification variable was measured using five statements. The lowest average score of 3.16 fell into the good category, indicating that respondents were skilled at taking quick and appropriate action when problems arose at work. The highest average score of 3.28 fell into the very good category, indicating that respondents were skilled at working together and maintaining a comfortable work environment.

The task complexity variable was measured using six statements. The lowest mean score of 2.63 fell into the good category, indicating that respondents felt the task was too difficult to complete with the existing AIS. The highest mean score of 3.23 fell into the good category, indicating that respondents clearly understood the task when carrying out the task.

The management support variable was measured using six statements. The lowest average score, 3.16, fell into the good category, indicating that respondents felt the AIS they used consistently received support to find solutions if the system wasn't working as intended.

The normality test was performed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. This test aims to determine whether the confounding factors or residuals in the regression model have a normal distribution. If the Asymp.sig coefficient (2-tailed) is greater than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$), the data is said to be normally distributed (Ghozali, 2018:184). The results of the normality test are shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Normality Test Results

	Unstandardized Residual
N	80
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	0.055
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

The results of the normality test using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test in Table 4.6 obtained a significance value of 0.200, greater than 0.05. This means that the regression equation model in this study is normally distributed.

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether a correlation exists between independent variables in the regression model. The test is based on the tolerance value and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the tolerance value is >0.01 or the VIF value is <10 , the model is considered free from multicollinearity (Ghozali, 2018:157). The results of the multicollinearity test are shown in Table 4 below:

Table 4. Results of Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Collinearity Tolerance	Statistics VIF	Information
Competency Certification (X1)	0.758	1,320	Multicollinearity Free
Task Complexity (X2)	0.867	1,153	Multicollinearity Free
Management Support (X3)	0.725	1,380	Multicollinearity Free

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Based on Table 4, it shows that the tolerance value of all variables is greater than 0.10 and the VIF value of all variables is less than 10. This can be concluded that the regression equation model is free from multicollinearity elements.

The heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether there is inequality in the variance of residuals from one observation to another in the regression model. The test is conducted using the Glejser test, which indicates that if the significance level of each independent variable is greater than 0.05, heteroscedasticity is not present (Ghozali, 2018:178). The results of the multicollinearity test are shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variables	Sig	Information
Competency Certification (X1)	0.401	Free of Heteroscedasticity
Task Complexity (X2)	0.106	Free of Heteroscedasticity
Management Support (X3)	0.935	Free of Heteroscedasticity

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Table 5 shows that the significance value for all variables is greater than 0.05. This concludes that there is no influence between the independent variables on the absolute residual, and the regression model does not contain heteroscedasticity. The results of the classical assumption test indicate that all requirements have been met, allowing the regression analysis to be used and discussed further.

Multiple linear regression analysis was used to analyze the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable. Table 6 below shows the results of the multiple linear regression analysis.

Table 6. Results of Hypothesis Testing with Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	4,841	2,773		1,746	0.085
Competency Certification	1,165	0.161	0.528	7,222	0,000
Task Complexity	0.381	0.113	0.231	3,383	0.001
Management Support	0.455	0.112	0.303	4,050	0,000

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis presented in Table 6, the following regression equation was created:

$$Y = 4.841 + 1.165X_1 + 0.381X_2 + 0.455X_3 + \varepsilon$$

The model feasibility test (F-test) aims to determine whether the independent variables have a simultaneous effect on the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018:98). The test was conducted using a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha = 5\%$). If the significance value is ≤ 0.05 , then the research regression model is considered fit for testing and indicates a simultaneous influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the model feasibility test (F-test) are shown in Table 7:

Table 7. Results of Model Feasibility Test (F Test)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3679,579	3	1226,526	56,909	.000b
Residual	1637,971	76	21,552		
Total	5317,550	79			

Source: Processed Primary Data, 2025

Based on Table 7, it shows that the calculated F value is 56.909 with a significance value of 0.000, which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$. This means that the regression model in this study is suitable for use and has a simultaneous influence between competency certification, task complexity, and management support on the effectiveness of the accounting information system.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) test aims to measure the model's ability to explain variations in the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018:97). The results of the coefficient of determination (R^2) test are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.832a	0.692	0.680	4,642

Source: Primary Data Processed 2025

Table 8 shows that the adjusted R-square value is 0.680. This concludes that 68% of the variation in competency certification, task complexity, and management support can explain the effectiveness of accounting information systems. The remaining 32% can be explained by other variables outside this study.

The t-test aims to analyze the influence of competency certification variables, task complexity, and management support on the effectiveness of accounting information systems. The t-value is a criterion in testing to determine the relationship between variables. If the t-value is ≤ 0.05 , the hypothesis is accepted, indicating that the independent variable has an effect on the dependent variable. If the t-value is > 0.05 , the hypothesis is rejected, indicating that the independent variable has no effect on the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018:98). The results of the analysis related to the influence of competency certification on the effectiveness of accounting information systems show a significance value of 0.000 with a regression coefficient of 1.165. The significance value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 and the regression coefficient is positive, indicating that the competency certification variable has a positive effect on the effectiveness of accounting information systems.

The analysis results related to the influence of task complexity on the effectiveness of accounting information systems show a significance value of 0.000 with a regression coefficient of 0.381. The significance value of 0.001 is smaller than 0.05 and the positive regression coefficient indicates that the task complexity variable has a positive effect on the effectiveness of accounting information systems.

The analysis results related to the influence of management support on the effectiveness of accounting information systems show a significance value of 0.000 with a regression coefficient of 0.455. The significance value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05 and the regression coefficient is positive indicating that the management support variable has a positive effect on the effectiveness of accounting information systems.

The Influence of Competency Certification on the Effectiveness of Accounting Information Systems

The first hypothesis (H1) proposed states that competency certification has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of the AIS at the Denpasar City KSP. Based on the research results in Table 4.12, H1 of this study is proven true, or in other words, H1 is accepted. This indicates that the more employees who participate in competency certification, the greater the effectiveness of the AIS. Competency certification has a positive impact on improving employee performance, empowerment, knowledge, and credibility, resulting in a better and more targeted AIS.

The results of this study support the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which explains the factors that determine the acceptance of information technology use, where system users tend to use the system if the system is easy to use and useful for them. Cooperative employees who have competency certification tend to feel they have competent knowledge and skills to support the use of information systems and perceive AIS to be easier to use. The results of this study are in line with research by Qudah, (2015) who stated that professional qualifications have a positive and highly significant influence on the effectiveness of AIS. The results of research by Ammar, (2025) stated that a professional accountant has a positive influence on accounting information systems. The results of research by Lestari & Fauzi, (2023), Numberi, (2022), (Athambawa & Teng, 2018) and Paranoan et al., (2019) stated that competence has a positive influence on the effectiveness of AIS.

The Influence of Task Complexity on the Effectiveness of Accounting Information Systems

The proposed hypothesis (H2) states that task complexity negatively impacts the effectiveness of the accounting information system at the Denpasar City Savings and Loans Cooperative. Based on the research results in Table 4.12, H2 of this study is not proven true or in other words, it means H2 is rejected. This indicates that the higher the level of complexity of employee tasks, the effectiveness of the accounting information system at the Denpasar City Savings and Loans Cooperative will increase. These results indicate that the high complexity of the tasks faced can be handled well by employees because employees have participated in competency certification so that the increasing complexity of the tasks can be overcome and the organization has provided supporting facilities for the accounting information system that are useful for employees to complete their work.

The results of this study support the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which explains the factors that determine the acceptance of the use of information technology where system users tend to use the system if the system is easy to use and useful for them. If the tasks that must be done by employees are considered complex, employees believe that the system can help them in completing complex tasks, so that employees will be more motivated to use the system because the right technology can improve user performance in completing tasks.

The results of this study are in line with research by (Putri et al., 2022), (Nugroho et al., 2018), (Suputra et al., 2021), (Pradana & Wirawati, 2018), and (Paramitha &

Supadmi, 2023) which state that task complexity has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of accounting information systems.

The Influence of Management Support on the Effectiveness of Accounting Information Systems

The third hypothesis (H₃) proposed states that management support has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the accounting information system. Based on the research results in Table 4.12, H₃ of this study is proven true, or in other words, H₃ is accepted. This indicates that the higher the management support, the greater the effectiveness of the accounting information system. These results indicate that the high level of management support and contribution provided by management, such as the availability of supporting facilities and opportunities to participate in competency certification given to employees in completing their work, can make a significant contribution to increasing the effectiveness of the accounting information system at Savings and Loan Cooperatives in Denpasar City.

The results of this study support the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which explains the factors that determine the acceptance of information technology use. System users tend to use a system if the system is easy to use and useful for them. One factor that influences technology adoption by users is facilitating conditions. When management provides training support to employees such as the provision of resources, training, and clear communication regarding the benefits of the system so that users can utilize the accounting information system optimally, which in turn increases the effectiveness of the system.

I. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the research results and analysis that have been described, it can be concluded that competency certification, task complexity, and management support have a positive effect on the effectiveness of AIS. The competency certification variable shows that the more employees participate in certification, the more effective AIS will be. The task complexity variable shows that the higher the complexity of the tasks faced by system users, the more effective AIS will be. The management support variable shows that the higher the management support provided, the more effective AIS will be.

Therefore, it is recommended that the management of KSP Kota Denpasar should provide the opportunity to participate in bookkeeper competency certification to all employees, especially those directly involved in the use of AIS, to improve employee capabilities and as employee professionalism in the field of accounting. The management of KSP Kota Denpasar is expected to provide job responsibilities to employees according to their abilities in order to minimize the emergence of individual perceptions about complex and complicated tasks and is expected to always participate and be involved in improving the development of AIS so that not only support from human resources but also from the system implemented the effectiveness of the accounting information system can be realized in each cooperative.

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